

THE ROLE OF TYPES OF PROJECTS IN THE FIELD OF
INNOVATIVE MANAGEMENT AND THEIR CLASSIFICATION

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Annotation

This article analyzes the types of projects implemented in the management of innovation processes, the stages and sequence of their implementation. The study also created a classification of projects to reveal the "from idea to commercialization" principle.

Keywords: Innovation, management, innovative management, startup, technology, fundamental, practical, commercialization, project.

Introduction.

Today, the development of new technologies in the global economy and increasing competition in the markets for goods, services and labor force are aimed at further improving and organizing the management of innovation processes in enterprises and organizations, as well as large companies. In particular, the modernization of the country's economy, the development of science-intensive driver industries is becoming one of the priorities to increase the competitiveness of the national economy. Since independence, our country has done a lot to modernize, diversify and increase production and expand the range of competitive products in domestic and foreign markets.

The rapid development of all spheres of society and state life requires the implementation of reforms based on modern innovative ideas, developments and technologies that will ensure the rapid and quality progress of our country on the path to becoming a leader of world civilization. In this regard, the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, The Ministry of Innovation Development was established by the Decree No. PF-5264 of November 29, 2017 "On the establishment of the Ministry of Innovation Development of the Republic of Uzbekistan" [1]. Ten

months later, the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan PF-5544 "On approval of the Strategy of Innovative Development of the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2019-2021" was issued [2].

According to the Decree, the main goal of the human capital development strategy is to determine the level of competitiveness and innovative development of the country in the international arena. achieving access to the ranks was identified as one of the main tasks. In this regard, in order to further accelerate the development of innovation processes, the laws of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Science and Scientific Activity" and "On Innovative Activity" were adopted [3, 4]. Based on the above, one of our most pressing tasks today is to further improve the field of innovation management in the effective management of innovation processes in our country, to dramatically increase the pace of development of the industry.

Research methodology

The methodological basis of the research is the application of the principle of "from idea to commercialization" in the field of innovation management in a comprehensive approach to the analysis of problems in the process of project sequencing. Based on the results of the analysis, a detailed classification of project types involved in innovative activities will be disclosed.

Analysis and results

Foreign and local scientists have conducted various studies to develop new solutions and proposals to improve innovation. They have devoted most of their research to the definition and classification of a particular type of project. This situation makes it difficult for some innovation management professionals to properly design an innovation system. M.S. Ochkovskaya and N.M. Rasulov, based on the analysis of BB Mullaboev, one of the developed countries, was noted by U.S. economists that "the innovation process is an activity that combines science, technology, entrepreneurship and management, aimed at the

commercialization of innovation." According to them, the process of innovation includes the stage from the emergence of the idea to the process of its implementation on a commercial basis (5.6).

According to Y.Shumpeter, one of the first scientists to study the problems associated with innovative processes and propose solutions, innovative changes can be brought to the market from the point of view of enterprises by providing production on the basis of new techniques and technological processes. , the right way to study the creation of new types of products, ie the use of raw materials, improving the organization of production and the provision of new innovative goods in the direction of opening new consumer markets mentioned (7.8).

In Uzbekistan, a lot of research has been conducted on the development of "Innovation Management" and the effective conduct of this process. In particular, in the textbook "Innovation Management", published by F.M.Matmurodov and R.I.Gimush, the development of new technical solutions for innovative processes, the development of research and development in priority sectors of the economy, the introduction of new products, increasing product competitiveness, production noted that this can be done by improving the technology in the process (8). Also, F. Ergashev, D.Rakhimova and Sh. Zaynutdinov studied the scientific and theoretical aspects of the development of innovation management, the foundations of the formation of the national innovation system were created by R.Aminov, A. Kadyrov and A.Rasulov (9). In general, there is a lot of scientific and methodological research on the management of innovation processes. However, there is almost no research to explain the sequence of project types based on the principle of "from idea to commercialization" for the effective implementation of this area. According to the analysis, the principle of "from idea to commercialization" includes several types of projects:

- Fundamental project;
- Practical project;

- Innovative project;
- Preparation project for commercialization;

Fundamental project - a theoretical and (or) experimental study aimed at gaining new knowledge about the basic laws of nature, society and human structure, formation and development, the relationship between them, as well as the study of objects created as a result of certain activities 'Transitional research [10]. So, based on our analysis, a fundamental project is the first stage of an innovation process, in which the mathematical, physical, and other processes that take place before a given idea of developing a network or building a new network becomes a prototype. to develop computational work, models, technological schemes and laws in other types of science. As a result of the fundamental project, a scientifically based model of the idea, a mock-up of the development and a laboratory copy are created (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Stages of implementation of fundamental projects.

An applied project is understood to serve to create or improve existing designs, materials, methods, services in production and / or social, as well as other sectors of the economy. The practical project will also promote the shape of the

real sector of the economy, ensure energy and resource savings in manufacturing, increase the innovative content and added value of products based on the needs of national economic entities [10].

Preparation of samples of high-tech products and the results of technical and technological tests of developments and the preparation of the obtained scientific and technical results for implementation in the real sector of the economy. In general, in the process of practical design, the mathematical model and calculations obtained as a result of the fundamental project, as well as an experimental copy of the development are made and tested, as well as the experimental results are summarized, the necessary documents are prepared and an industrial copy of the development is prepared.

Figure 2. Sequence of practical project execution

The innovative project is aimed at creating new import-substituting, export-oriented products and technologies using local raw materials based on previous fundamental and applied research, as well as improving the quality of existing ones, reducing costs, creating new jobs in the labor market [10]. The design, preparation and testing of design, experimental samples, instruments, materials, products and other scientific works, which are then carried out for the practical use of the results of the innovative project, are used in the implementation of innovative experimental design work related to development. In general, in the process of innovative project, a scientific basis, mathematical model and experimental copy created as a result of fundamental and applied projects, as well as an industrial copy of the development are created and introduced into

production based on the test results. Also, during the implementation of the innovative project, accreditation, licensing and certification of development and other types of documentation will be carried out (11).

Figure 3. Stages of implementation of innovative projects

A commercialization project is the process of bringing a new type of product or service to market. In fact, a commercialization project is implemented when a small business is established and allows it to enter a larger market [12]. Many researchers in the field of commercialization management have come to different conclusions and recommendations based on their research (13,14,15). According to him, first a new product is invented or something new is invented. Evaluation of a new invention or discovery is carried out, ie the technical novelty of the product, intellectual property rights (patent purity) and the business potential of the product are analyzed and evaluated. Following the evaluation, the copyright of a new invention or discovery is protected by obtaining a patent. The next step is to develop and test a prototype of the product based on the patent obtained. Once the tests are successful and the product is justified, a new spin-off will be created to implement the project. After that, the final decision on the implementation of the commercialization project will be made. It can be done in three ways: licensing intellectual property, selling intellectual property, and producing one's own product. Production can also be done in three different ways, which are self-financing of the product, production with the help of sponsors, control of sales and management in the market, product improvement and production (Figure 4).

Figure 4. The spinn-off model sequence of the commercialization process.

As can be seen from the above diagram, the implementation of commercialization projects requires a number of processes after the idea is born and becomes a product on the market. In such cases, proper planning of innovation processes is one of the important factors.

In conclusion, from the above considerations and analysis, it is necessary to correctly define the sequence of projects in the implementation of the principle of "from idea to commercialization" as an important factor in the management of innovation processes, otherwise the product may be poor quality and low level of innovation. rsatadi. This is because launching production of a prototype without a scientific basis directly after the idea can lead to the inefficiency of commercialization projects, so in the management of innovation processes, It is expedient to work on the principle of "from idea to commercialization" rather than "prototype", in which the sequence of projects is first fundamental, then practical and innovative, then commercialization projects. In this way, the management of innovation processes is significantly effective .

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